

The Guided Self-Correction to Improve Indonesian EFL Students' Writing Achievement

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ABSTRACT: The current research aimed to identify the effect of the guided self-correction on students' writing achievement. The study employed a quantitative design. The subject was 1 class which consisted of 31 students. This research used a purposive sampling method. The data were collected through the pre-test and post-test in the form of writing tests. The data from both pre and the post-tests were compared using SPSS 25.0. The results showed there was a statistically significant difference of students' writing achievement when the students taught by guided self-correction with the significant level, 0.03. That is, when the students provided with the guided self-correction had better writing achievement. Therefore, the guided self-correction had statistically significant effects on the students' descriptive writing achievement. The findings suggest that the guided could be implemented to facilitate students to improve their descriptive writing achievement.

KEYWORDS: Descriptive Text, Guided Self-Correction, Indonesian EFL Students, Self-Correction, Writing Achievement.

INTRODUCTION

Academic writing ability is a competency that must be possessed by Indonesian EFL learners. However, students' writing ability is generally unsatisfactory. It is caused by the EFL learners still making some errors in writing, especially regarding five aspects such as content, grammar, vocabulary, mechanics, and organization. This phenomenon reflects on students' writing ability in Indonesia which is still relatively low (Kalidjernih, 2010; Widodo, Jaelani, Novitasari, Sutisna and Erfan, 2020). This condition requires the right solution to improve students' academic writing.

One of the factors is they are not actively involved in the learning process and the teacher does not provide opportunities for them to be active in learning. Nunan (2003) states that the teacher should provide opportunities for students to write. It can be journal entries, letter writing, summaries, poetry, or any type of writing that teachers find useful to practice in writing class. These obstacles show the importance of learning strategies that can facilitate students to be actively involved in the learning process.

Nowadays, most of the language teaching and learning process in every institution applies teacher correction, peer correction and self-correction techniques. These strategies are often used to help students improve their writing quality. It involves students' active role in the learning process. Research on self-correction continues to be relatively interesting. Cahyono and Amrina (2016) conducted research on peer feedback, self-correction and writing proficiency of Indonesian EFL students. Adi, et.al (2017) conducted research on the use of self-correction in teaching recount text. Another research was conducted by Lengkoan and Olli (2020). They studied self-correction in writing paragraphs. These show the important roles of peer and self-corrections in helping students improve their writing quality.

However, those research have a limited correction process either by peers or by self-correction without providing a guide that needs to be corrected such as content, organization, vocabulary, language use and mechanics. It causes the proofreader to focus less on aspects that need improvement. This finding supports the finding by Cahyono and Amrina (2016) who stated that the guidance sheet would be a crucial factor in doing self-correction. The guidance sheet was also made as how it was. It was done by considering that the guidance sheet should cover what the students were going to achieve. In the current research, the researcher developed self-correction strategies by providing a guide that is related to writing aspects so that the students more focused on what they are correcting. Therefore, this study constructs the research question as follows; What is the effect of guided self-correction on students' writing achievement?

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Heaton (1991), writing is one of the productive language skills that might be a complex problem for all teachers and students, since several aspects should be gained such as content, grammar, vocabulary, mechanics, and organization. By writing, they will be able to express their ideas, feelings, attitudes, etc. on paper. In doing this activity they communicate what they have in their mind without talking about it. In addition, writing helps students to improve and maintain their vocabulary and most importantly, writing can help students to think creatively.

Self-Correction

According to Nation (2008), self-correction is a technique where the learners should correct their mistakes themselves by checking their work carefully. Andrade and Du (2007), explain that self-correction technique is a process in which students reflect on and evaluate the quality of their work and their learning, know explicitly stated goals or criteria, assess their work for strengths and faults, and update it. It means the self-correction technique enhances students' knowledge of their work based on the self-correction technique guidance sheet. Furthermore, Harmer (2004) states that correction is a fascinating process in the teacher-student relationship in the classroom.

In addition, Maftoon and Shirazi (2010) argue the self-correction technique is an indirect feedback in which the teacher provides students with options so that they can determine the correct form on their own. In addition, the self-correction technique consists of two basic activities: (1) monitoring and evaluating the quality of their thoughts and behavior during learning, and (2) identifying ways to enhance their understanding and abilities (Mcmillan & Hearn, 2008).

The Weaknesses of Self-Correction

Some studies state that the self-correction technique is not ideal for some reasons to enhance students' results in writing. According to Covil (2010), it is potentially more time-consuming. The teacher should consider the time that will be used in correcting the text. It is potential to give the time allocation with standard of symbol so the time can be used to correct the mistakes only.

In addition, Andrade and Du (2005) state that self-correction technique has some disadvantages. They are:

1. Additional briefing time can increase a teacher's workload.
When the teacher uses the self-correction technique, it requires briefing time or some instruction to correct their work because the student has a lack of knowledge about correction especially aspects of writing. It means the teacher requires a lot of time to teach them about self-correction itself and aspects of writing at the time. It can waste many times.
2. The validity and reliability are low.
The student still has a subjective assessment. It can be said they do not yet have a precise and clear measurement. It affects the validity and reliability are low. When the teacher uses the self-correction technique, they have to provide precise and clear measurements that are easier to understand by a student what they will do and what they will measure.
3. Students feel ill-equipped to undertake the Self-Correction technique.
It can be said that the student does not have a lot of material to correct their work so the student feels unprepared. The teacher should make the same material preparation for all students. So, the students are not confused and not insecure because they have different knowledge.
4. Students may be reluctant to make judgments regarding their work.
The students feel afraid, lack confidence, and doubts their ability. This is because they are not actively involved in learning and the teacher does not provide opportunities to be active in learning so they tend to be afraid of giving wrong judgments about themselves.

In conclusion, based on the whole of weaknesses of self-correction, the researcher decides to focus on one weakness; it is the student feeling ill-equipped to undertake the self-correction technique. The researcher should provide the same material preparation for all students. So, the students are not confused and not insecure because they have different knowledge.

Guided Self-Correction

White and Arndt (1991: 4) develop the learning materials based on the process orientation. According to them, some things must be taken by the researcher in developing the idea. They are generating ideas, developing a focus, structuring, drafting, evaluating, and reviewing.

Guided self-correction is self-correction accompanied by a guide made by a teacher. It is arranged based on an explanation of writing aspects by Jacobs (1981) and consists of five components of writing; content, organization, vocabulary, language use, and mechanics. Besides, this guide refers to language features of descriptive text consisting of identification, description, and grammatical features.

Concept		
Generic Structure		
Identification Description	Underline the specific place!	Bromo Mountain.
	Underline a sentence that describes a specific characteristic/ idea!	Bromo Mountain is one of an active volcano. It is located around 2,5 hours from Malang city.
	Underline a sentence that does not describe a specific characteristic/ idea!	The location of Marina Beach is South Lampung.
	Underline a sentence that has a relevant idea with the title!	The view of Bromo Mountain is beautiful. The visitors can see many fogs there.
	Underline a sentence that has no relevant idea with the title!	Many spinaches grow well there.
Language Features		
Word forms	Noun: common suffixes -tion, -ity, -ance, -er, -ness, -ism, etc. Make it correct if necessary!	Education, community, importance, business, criticism, relationship
	Verb: common suffixes -ize, -ate, -fy, etc. Make it correct if necessary!	Realize, differentiate, satisfy
	Adjective: common suffixes -al, -ent, -ful, -ive, -less, etc. Make it correct if necessary!	General, independent, beautiful, positive, helpless
	Adjective: common suffixes: -ly Make it correct if necessary!	Exactly, clearly, simply, finally
Subject Verb Agreement in Simple Present Tense	<u>Verbal</u> Plural: S (I, you, they, we) + V1+ O/C Singular: S (He, She, It) + V1 (+s/es) + O/C Make it grammatically correct if necessary!	They ride in a car together. She rides a car together.
	<u>Nominal</u> S (I) + am + O/C S (you, they, we) + are + O/C S (He, She, It) + is + O/C Make it grammatically correct if necessary!	I am very happy. We are strong. It is beautiful.
Articles	-“A” is used in front of singular countables (Person, animal or thing) which are not specific. -If a noun starts with a consonant sound (b, c, d, etc.) “A” comes before the noun. Make it grammatically correct if necessary!	a cat, a bird, a child, a car
	-“An” is used in front of singular countable (Person, animal, or thing) that are not specific.	an apple, an egg, an ant

	-If a noun starts with a vowel sound (a, i, u, e, o) “An” comes before the noun. Make it grammatically correct if necessary!	
	“The” is used in front of all nouns to describe something specific. Make it grammatically correct if necessary!	the weather, the sky, the mountain
Prepositions	Preposition of Place: At/In: address, building, area’s name, On: position. Make it grammatically correct if necessary!	I play at/in the mall. I put my phone on the table.
	Preposition of Time: At: time, On: day, In: month, year, weather. Make it grammatically correct if necessary!	I take a bath every day at 6 am. I’m going to the sea on Monday. I go to the sea in 2023
	Preposition of Direction: Into: direction (already), Toward: direction (prepare). Make it grammatically correct if necessary!	He jumps into the sea. She comes toward you.
Punctuation	Every sentence ends with a period (.). Make it correct if necessary!	Mr. Smith takes some of <u>Edelweiss</u> .
	Every sentence has a different meaning ends with a full stop (.). Make it correct if necessary!	Bromo Mountain is one of an active <u>volcano</u> . It is located around 2,5 hours from Malang <u>city</u> .
	Every sentence uses a colon (:) to end the complete statement and is followed by details. Make it correct if necessary!	They visit many places there; Bukit Teletubies, Pasir Berbisik, Bukite Cinta, etc.
	Every sentence uses a comma (,) to mention the things that are more than two. Make it correct if necessary!	You will need a jacket, gloves, shawl, etc.
Capitalization	Every sentence starts with a capital letter. Make it correct if necessary!	<u>Bromo</u> Mountain is one of an active volcano.
	Every title of the text starts with a capital letter except for short prepositions and coordinating conjunctions, Make it correct if necessary!	Bromo Mountain
	Every pronoun “I” uses a capital letter. Make it correct if necessary!	My friend and <u>I</u> are always happy.
	Every name of detail starts with a capital letter. Make it correct if necessary!	The name of Bromo is taken from the name of one of the <u>Gods</u> of Hinduism, Brahma.
	Every name of people and their title starts with a capital letter. Make it correct if necessary!	We go with our teacher. It is <u>Mr. Smith, S.Pd</u> .
	Every name of the specific place starts with a capital letter. Make it correct if necessary!	They visit many places there; <u>Bukit Teletubies, Pasir Berbisik, Bukite Cinta, etc.</u>
	Every name of day, month, and special day starts with a capital letter. Make it correct if necessary!	The students visit Bromo Mountain on <u>Monday</u> .
Every name of a specific group of people, language, and religion starts with a capital letter. Make it correct if necessary!	There are many students of Mapala climbing together.	

	Every name of a geographic area starts with a capital letter. Make it correct if necessary!	It is located around 2,5 hours from <u>Malang city.</u>
	Every name of a specific structure such as buildings and bridges starts with a capital letter. Make it correct if necessary!	Before we climb a mountain, we pray together in <u>Al-Hidayah Mosque.</u>
Spelling	Find and underline a word that is misspelled. Make it correct if necessary!	Mountain X Montain

Procedure of Teaching Descriptive Text Through Guided Self-Correction

Here are some stages to teach descriptive text through guided self-correction:

Stage 1: Pre-writing/Planning

1. The teacher explains the descriptive text.
2. The teacher gives some pictures of tourist places.
3. The teacher gives some questions to the students related to tourism place pictures.
4. The teacher gives an example of the use of simple present tense in descriptive text.

This section refers to brainstorming a narrow topic to a particular aspect of the general one. Doing this will give the student new knowledge.

Stage 2: Writing

1. The teacher asks the student to choose one of the pictures.
2. The students pay attention to the picture that they have chosen.
3. The teacher instructs them to describe an interesting tourist place that students want to write about and provides information to follow the generic structure of the descriptive text.

No	Title	Idea	General information	Specific Information
1
Description :				

This section refers to free writing. Doing this will make the students' writing clear. It means that which does not explain this step the student will be confused.

Stage 3: Revising (Guided self-correction)

1. The teacher instructs students to read their writing individually.
2. The teacher asks students to observe their writing.
3. After observing, the teacher asks students to check their writing, and students begin to be aware of something weird about their writing by considering guided self-correction.
4. The teacher encourages and asks students to check whether there were any mistakes in their writing by considering guided self-correction.
5. The teacher asks students to correct their mistakes.
6. The teacher re-checked the corrections made by the students.

This section refers to making a model of self-correction using a guide made by the teacher to facilitate the student in the revising stage.

METHODS

This current research is a quantitative method. It aims to identify the effect of the guided self-correction on students' writing achievement. The students' writing achievement was measured based on the aspects which are basis of content, organization, vocabulary, language use, and mechanics. The population of the research was 5 classes in the first grade of SMAN 1 Seputih Mataram. The sample was 1 class; 31 students. It used a purposive sampling method. To know students' writing ability, the

researcher used a writing test in the form of pretest and posttest. The text included was descriptive text. It was calculated through the Paired Samples T-Test with Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

This section presents the findings and analysis derived from the research. The result of frequently score of control and experiment class is presented as follow:

Frequently Scores, Mean and Gains of Students' Writing

No	Scores	Pretest	Posttest
1	40 – 49	8	0
2	50 – 59	14	0
3	60 – 69	6	2
4	70 – 79	3	16
5	80 – 89	0	13
Means		55.1	78.8
Gain		23.6	

The table showed that the scores between 40-49, pretest had 8 students and posttest had nothing. The scores 50-59, pretest had 14 students and posttest had nothing. The scores 60-69, pretest had 6 students, posttest had 2 students. The scores 70-79, pretest had 3 students' and posttest had 16 students. The scores 80-89, pretest had nothing and posttest had 13 students.

It means that the most frequent score in pretest was 50-59 and posttest control was 70-79. Moreover, the mean score of pretest is 55.1 and the posttest is 78.8 with gain 23.6.

The Improvement of Students' Descriptive Writing Ability in Using Guided Self-Correction

The Difference of Mean between the Pretest and Posttest of the Guided Self-Correction

Paired Samples Statistics					
		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	PRETEST	55.1935	31	8.01007	1.43865
	POSTTEST	78.8710	31	5.84090	1.04906

The table showed that the scores of students' pretest to posttest in the control class; Unguided Self-Correction is improved. The mean score of pretest in the control class is 55.19 and the posttest is 78.87 with a gain 23.68 which means there is a statistically significant difference in students' scores before and after the treatment using Unguided Self-Correction.

Statistical Calculation of Students' Writing between the Pretest and Posttest of the Guided Self-Correction

Paired Samples Test									
		Paired Differences					T	df	
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
Pair 1	Pretest posttest				Lower	Upper			
		-23.67742	9.32519	1.67485	-27.09793	-20.25691	-14.137	30	.000

The table showed that t-value is higher than the t-table $14.137 > 2.036$ and with the level significance $p < 0.05$ and sig. 2 tailed was 0.000. This suggests that teaching through guided self-correction can improve students' descriptive writing achievement.

The Improvement of Guided Self-Correction and Unguided Self-Correction in Students' Descriptive Text Writing Ability

The result of this research showed that the difference between the two scores was found to be statistically significant indicating that the guided self-correction treatment made a significant improvement. This indicates that the guided self-correction could have a greater significant effect in improving students' descriptive writing.

As shown in the findings in the pretest the majority of the students made errors regarding omission particularly when the subject is a noun, for example, Bromo so very beautiful. But the students then could make self-corrections on the errors they encountered as shown in the excerpt of the text, Bromo is so very beautiful. Most students only focus on one or two errors.

Meanwhile, the majority of students found many errors when they facilitated with guidance. Not only grammatically, but the students also found errors in mechanics, for example, my friend and i, this so beautiful, bromo mountain. After making self-corrections and considering the guide, the students changed these errors. My friend and I, Bromo Mountain, this is so beautiful. Capital letter and full stop after end of sentence is needed.

Moreover, the guide provided much information about the writing aspects as content. In posttest the students gave information about location, for example, It is located in Malang City. Then, they added the distance from Malang. It is located around 2,5 hours from Malang City.

Based on the result of the score distribution, and also the analysis of the scores, it was proved that there was improvement of the students' scores. This could not be separated with the use of a guidance sheet. This finding supports the finding by Cahyono and Amrina (2016) who stated that the guidance sheet would be a crucial factor in doing self-correction. The guidance sheet was also made as how it was. It was done considering that the guidance sheet should covered what the students were going to achieve. Self-correction with the guidance sheet helped the students to improve their writing achievement positively. This finding was in line with the previous studies (Baradaran & Alavi, 2015) which state that self-correction gave a positive impact on students writing achievement.

In reality, most of the students were not able to understand what they needed to do, and because of that, they were not doing the self-correction wholeheartedly. It could be seen as the researcher observed the students while they were doing the self-correction. The researcher also paid attention in private to what they said while they were correcting their work. Some students were seen to be seriously revising their work, and it could be seen that their responsibility and independence toward their tasks were increasing. It supports the theories; as stated in the previous chapter of this research that self-correction builds the tendency of the students to be independent and responsible of their own work (Spiller, 2012).

However, a student could not assess their own work without evaluative knowledge or guidelines on how to do so effectively. For self-monitoring to be successful, students need criteria, standards, or goals (Taras, 2005) which allow them to adequately judge the quality of their work, and they should be able to choose various strategies on how to improve their performance in the future (Sadler, 1989). By allowing students the opportunity to self-monitor, guided self-correction can give them evaluative knowledge. Generally, guided self-correction can facilitate students to engage in their improvement.

In conclusion, guided self-correction has more advantages on students' descriptive writing ability. This finding answered the research question which is what is the effect of guided self-correction on students' writing achievement and the answer is there is improvement in the students after being introduced to guided self-correction.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

This study investigated the effects of guided self-correction on students' descriptive writing ability. Specifically, it tried to determine if there was a significant difference between providing guidance for correction and without providing guidance. Guided self-correction can lead students toward better improvement in descriptive writing. When self-correction is applied with proper guidance, self-correction can increase the evaluative knowledge essential for achievement and indicate various strategies on how to get there. Generally, in this study, it was discovered that guided self-correction was more helpful for students' improvement.

About the conclusions above, the following implications are recommended: Suggestions for English Teachers. 1) English teachers should utilize varied ways of corrective feedback provision strategies and give opportunities for independent learning by indicating the location and type of errors. 2) English teachers should oversee students' writing attempts throughout the overall writing process with corrective feedback provision. 3) In corrective feedback provision, students should be given wider opportunities to revise their drafts, act on the feedback engaging them, and self-correct themselves. 4) English teachers should help students discover their

independent learning through feedback provision. Suggestions for Further Research. 1) Further researches should consider the individual differences and learning outcomes, such as awareness of students' needs and the objectives of the lesson. 2) Further researches should focus on teachers' and students' perspectives

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